

Thermal Effect on Vibration of Non- Homogeneous Orthotropic Trapezoidal Plate with Thickness Varies Parabolically In Both Directions

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Abstract- The objective of present paper is to study the thermal effect on vibration of non- homogeneous orthotropic trapezoidal plate with thickness varies parabolically in both directions. For non-homogeneity of the plate density is assumed linearly in x-direction. Using Rayleigh-Ritz method governing differential equation has been attained by taking two term deflection function corresponding to clamped-simply supported clamped-simply supported (C-S-C-S) boundary conditions. The effects of structural parameters such as taper constant, non-homogeneity constant, aspect ratio and thermal gradient have also been studied. Results are calculated with great accuracy and compare the present model with the other in literature with the help of tables.

Keywords- Thermal gradient, non-homogeneous, vibration, density, thickness etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gupta and Kumud [1] analysed the thermal effect on vibration of non-homogeneous parallelogram plate of parabolically varying thickness. Chakraverty [2] studied the vibration of plates. Gupta et.al [3] studied the free vibration of clamped visco-elastic rectangular plate having bi-direction exponential thickness variations. Tomar et.al [4] studied the free vibrations of an isotropic nonhomogeneous infinite plate of parabolically varying thickness. Tomar and Gupta [5] studied the effect of thermal gradient on frequencies of an orthotropic rectangular plate whose thickness varies in two directions. Gutierrez et.al [6] studied the fundamental frequency of vibrating rectangular, non-homogeneous plates. Kumar [7] studied the free vibration analysis of isotropic rectangular plates on Winkler foundation using differential transform method. Gupta et.al [8] analysed the thermal gradient effect on vibrations of non-homogeneous rectangular plate having continuously parabolically varying thickness in both directions. Lal [9] studied the transverse vibrations of orthotropic non-uniform rectangular plate with

continuously varying density. Khani and Aziz [10] studied the thermal analysis of a longitudinal trapezoidal fin with temperature-dependent thermal conductivity and heat transfer coefficient. Mania [11] studied the buckling analysis of trapezoidal composite sandwich plate subjected to inplane compression. McGee et.al [12] studied the vibrations of cantilevered skewed trapezoidal and triangular plates with corner stress singularities. Gupta and Sharma [13] Studied the thermally induced vibration of non-homogeneous trapezoidal plate with varying thickness and density. Gupta and Sharma [14] studied the effect of linear thermal gradient on vibration of trapezoidal plates whose thickness varies parabolically. Gupta and Sharma [15] studied the thermal effect on frequencies of non-homogeneous trapezoidal plate with linearly varying thickness in one direction and linearly varying density in other direction. Tomar and Gupta [16] studied the effect of thermal gradient on frequencies of an orthotropic rectangular plate whose thickness varies in two directions. In the present study author measures the effect of non-homogeneity on thermally induced vibration of orthotropic trapezoidal plate with

thickness varies parabolically in both directions. For non-homogeneity of the plate density is assumed linearly in x-direction. Using Rayleigh-Ritz method governing differential equation has been attained by taking two term deflection function corresponding to clamped-simply supported clamped-simply supported (C-S-C-S) boundary condition. The effects of structural parameters such as taper constant, non-homogeneity constant, aspect ratio and thermal gradient have also been studied. Results are calculated with great accuracy and compare the present model with the other in literature with the help of tables.

II. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

Geometrical Representation

y,χ
b/2
c/2

oo o x,ξ
x,ζ

c/2
b/2

x,ζ
[[h]_0

a/2 z a/2
h(ζ)=h_0 [1-(1-δ_1)(ζ+1/2)^2][1-(1-δ_2)(χ+1/2)^2]

Geometry of orthotropic trapezoidal plate fig. 1

Temperature:

The general equation of temperature with linear temperature distribution in x-direction is

$$\theta = \theta_0 (1/2 - \zeta) \quad (3)$$

where θ and θ_0 denote the temperature excess above the reference temperature on the plate at any point and at the origin, respectively.

For most orthotropic materials, modulus of elasticity is described as a function of temperature as

$$\check{E}_\zeta(\theta) = \check{E}_1 (1 - \gamma\theta),$$

$$\begin{aligned} \check{E}_\chi(\theta) &= \check{E}_2 (1 - \gamma\theta), \\ G_\zeta\chi(\theta) &= G_0 (1 - \gamma\theta), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where \check{E}_ζ and \check{E}_χ are Young's moduli in x-direction and y-direction, respectively, and $G_\zeta\chi$ is the shear modulus, γ is slope of vibration of moduli with temperature, and \check{E}_1 , \check{E}_2 and G_0 are the values of moduli at some reference temperature; that is, θ=0.

Using (3), (4) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \check{E}_\zeta(\theta) &= \check{E}_1 (1 - \delta(1/2 - \zeta)), \\ G_\zeta\chi(\theta) &= G_0 (1 - \delta(1/2 - \zeta)), \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \check{E}_\chi(\theta) &= \check{E}_2 (1 - \delta(1/2 - \zeta)), \\ G_\zeta\chi(\theta) &= G_0 (1 - \delta(1/2 - \zeta)). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\delta = \gamma\theta_0$ (0 ≤ δ < 1) known as thermal gradient

Thickness and Density

For tapering in plate thickness has important role as compared to uniform thickness. The general equation of thickness with parabolic variation in both directions is

$$h(\zeta) = h_0 [1 - (1 - \delta_1)(\zeta + 1/2)^2][1 - (1 - \delta_2)(\chi + 1/2)^2] \quad (1)$$

where h_0 is the maximum plate thickness occurring at the left edge, δh_0 is the minimum plate thickness occurring at the right edge and δ_1, δ_2 are the taper constants.

For non-homogeneity of the plate density is assumed linear in x-direction. The general equation of density with linear variation in x-direction is

$$\rho = \rho_0 [1 - (1 - \beta)(\zeta + 1/2)] \quad (2)$$

where β is the non-homogeneity constant of the plate, ρ_0 is the mass density at ζ = -1/2.

Deflection function and corresponding boundary condition

Two term deflection function with boundary condition clamped simply supported- clamped

simply supported(C-S-C-S) for vibrational analysis has been considered and can be written as

$$\psi = P_1 \{(\zeta + 1/2)(\zeta - 1/2)\}^2 \{\chi - ((b-c)/2)\zeta + ((b+c)/4)\} + P_2 \{(\zeta + 1/2)(\zeta - 1/2)\}^3 \{\chi - ((b-c)/2)\zeta + ((b+c)/4)\}^2 \{\chi + ((b-c)/2)\zeta - ((b+c)/4)\}^2, \quad (6)$$

P_1 and P_2 are two unknown constants to be determined.

Thus, for all the non-homogeneous trapezoidal plate eq. (6) satisfied the following conditions clamped simply supported- clamped simply supported(C-S-C-S) for vibrational analysis such as

$$\begin{aligned} \chi &= c/4b - (\zeta)/2 + 1/4 + c\zeta/2b, \\ \chi &= -c/4b + (\zeta)/2 - 1/4 - c\zeta/2b, \\ \zeta &= -1/2, \zeta = 1/2, \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

introducing the following non-dimensional variables as $\zeta = x/a$ and $\chi = y/b$.

Governing Equation Becomes

Expression for maximum strain energy and maximum kinetic energy for orthotropic trapezoidal plate are [18] as

$$P = ab/2 \iint \left[\left[\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \chi} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \zeta^2} \right) \right]^2 + \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial \zeta} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \chi^2} \right) \right]^2 + 2 \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial \zeta} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \zeta^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \chi^2} \right) + 4 \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \chi} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \zeta \partial \chi} \right)^2 \right] d\zeta d\chi, \quad (8)$$

and

$$K = ab/2 \omega^2 h_0 \iint \left[\rho h (\zeta) \psi^2 \right] d\zeta d\chi, \quad (9)$$

where ω is the angular frequency of vibration.

Also flexural and torsion rigidity is given by Leissa [14] as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \chi} &= \left(\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \chi} h^3 \right) / 12(1 - \nu_{\chi} \nu_{\zeta}), \\ \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial \zeta} &= \left(\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial \zeta} h^3 \right) / 12(1 - \nu_{\chi} \nu_{\zeta}), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta \chi}{\partial \chi} = (G_{\zeta \chi} h^3) / 12.$$

Using (5), (10) becomes

$$\left[\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \chi} = \left(\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \chi} h^3 (1 - \delta(1/2 - \zeta)) \right) / 12(1 - \nu_{\chi} \nu_{\zeta}), \right. \\ \left. \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial \zeta} = \left(\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial \zeta} h^3 (1 - \delta(1/2 - \zeta)) \right) / 12(1 - \nu_{\chi} \nu_{\zeta}), \right] \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta \chi}{\partial \chi} = (G_0 h^3 (1 - \delta(1/2 - \zeta))) / 12.$$

Also

$$\left[\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \chi} = \nu_{\chi} \left[\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \chi} \right]_{\chi}, \right] \quad (12)$$

where h is the thickness of the plate.

After applying boundary conditions (7), (8) and (9) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} P &= ab/2 \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} \int_{-c/4b + (\zeta)/2 - 1/4 - c\zeta/2b}^{c/4b - (\zeta)/2 + 1/4 + c\zeta/2b} \left[\left[\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \chi} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \zeta^2} \right) \right]^2 + \left[\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial \zeta} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \chi^2} \right) \right]^2 + 2 \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial \zeta} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \zeta^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \chi^2} \right) + 4 \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \chi} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \zeta \partial \chi} \right)^2 \right] d\zeta d\chi \quad (13) \\ K &= ab/2 \omega^2 h_0 \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} \int_{-c/4b + (\zeta)/2 - 1/4 - c\zeta/2b}^{c/4b - (\zeta)/2 + 1/4 + c\zeta/2b} \left[\rho h (\zeta) \psi^2 \right] d\zeta d\chi \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

Rayleigh Ritz Technique

To obtain equation of frequency and vibrational frequency Rayleigh Ritz technique is used according to which

$$\delta(P - K) = 0 \quad \text{implies}$$

$$\delta(P_1 - \mu^2 K_1) = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &= \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} \int_{-c/4b + (\zeta)/2 - 1/4 - c\zeta/2b}^{c/4b - (\zeta)/2 + 1/4 + c\zeta/2b} \left[\left[1 - (1 - \delta_1) (\zeta + 1/2)^2 \right] \left[1 - (1 - \delta_2) (\chi + 1/2)^2 \right]^3 (1 - \delta(1/2 - \zeta)) \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \zeta^2} \right) \right]^2 + \left[\frac{E_2}{E_1} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \chi^2} \right) \right]^2 + 2 \nu_{\zeta} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \zeta^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \chi^2} \right) + 4 (G_0 (1 - \nu_{\chi} \nu_{\zeta})) / E_1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \zeta \partial \chi} \right)^2 \right] d\zeta d\chi \\ K_1 &= \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} \int_{-c/4b + (\zeta)/2 - 1/4 - c\zeta/2b}^{c/4b - (\zeta)/2 + 1/4 + c\zeta/2b} \left[\rho \left[1 - (1 - \delta_1) (\zeta + 1/2)^2 \right] \left[1 - (1 - \delta_2) (\chi + 1/2)^2 \right] \psi^2 \right] d\zeta d\chi \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Where} \quad \mu^2 = (12 \rho_0 \omega^2 a^5 (1 - \nu_{\chi} \nu_{\zeta})) / (\check{E}_1 [h_0]^2) \quad (16)$$

Equation (15) involves two constants C_1 and C_2 to be evaluated as follows

$$\left(\frac{\partial(P_1 - \mu^2 K_1)}{\partial C_m} \right) = 0 \quad ; \quad m = 1, 2 \quad (17)$$

On simplifying (16) We get

$$T_{m1} C_1 + T_{m2} C_2 = 0 \quad ; \quad m = 1, 2 \quad (18)$$

In this way the frequency equation can be obtained as

$$\left| \begin{matrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} \end{matrix} \right| = 0 \quad (19)$$

and results validated with preexisting literature. taper constant and thermal gradient. Taking non-Results and Discussion: With the help of homogeneity constant fixed $\beta=0.4$. Mathematica Software two values of frequency parameter are calculated for different values of

Table 3.1: In the following table values of frequency parameter μ for an orthotropic trapezoidal plate for different values of taper constant δ_1 and constant aspect ratios

δ_1	$\delta_2=0.0$				$\delta_2=0.6$			
	$\delta = 0.0$		$\delta = 0.4$		$\delta = 0.0$		$\delta = 0.4$	
	First Mode	Second Mode						
0.0	31.0007	159.776	24.8129	138.877	31.2282	162.329	25.1059	138.147
0.2	31.6241	163.223	25.6444	139.22	32.2035	166.097	26.2151	141.876
0.4	31.6599	167.184	25.8189	143.119	32.3456	170.404	26.4927	146.096
0.6	31.864	171.634	26.1648	147.462	32.6727	175.225	26.9594	150.786
0.8	32.2466	176.542	26.6934	152.224	33.1962	180.529	27.6271	155.92
1.0	32.8129	181.877	27.4084	157.377	33.9209	186.285	28.4989	161.468

Graph 3.1.1: Represents the first mode of frequency parameter μ for an orthotropic trapezoidal plate for different values of taper constant δ_1 and constant aspect ratios $a/b=1.0, (c)/b=0.5$, Non-homogeneity constant $\beta=0.4$, Thermal Gradient $\delta=0.0,0.4$ and Taper Constant $\delta_2=0.0,0.6$.

Graph 3.1.2: Represents the second mode frequency parameter μ for a orthotropic trapezoidal plate for different values of taper constant δ_1 and constant aspect ratios $a/b=1.0, (c)/b=0.5$, non-homogeneity constant $\beta=0.4$, Thermal Gradient $\delta=0.0,0.4$ and Taper Constant $\delta_2=0.0,0.6$.

Table 3.2 In the following table two different values of frequency parameter μ for an orthotropic trapezoidal plate for different values of taper constant δ_2 and constant aspect ratios $a/(b)=1.0, (c)/b=0.5$, $\beta=0.4$, Taper Constant $\delta_1=0.0,0.6$ are calculated.

Mode	$\delta_1=0.0$		$\delta_1=0.6$	
	$\delta=0.0$	$\delta=0.4$	$\delta=0.0$	$\delta=0.4$
First Mode	31.7407	159.776	25.6229	135.789
Second Mode	171.634	24.1648	143.462	31.864

δ_2	$\delta_1=0.0$				$\delta_1=0.6$			
	$\delta = 0.0$		$\delta = 0.4$		$\delta = 0.0$		$\delta = 0.4$	
	First Mode	Second Mode						
0.0	31.7407	159.776	25.6229	135.789	31.864	171.634	24.1648	143.462

0.0	31.7407	159.776	25.6229	135.789	31.864	171.634	24.1648	143.462
0.2	31.0856	156.282	25.1389	132.911	31.364	168.289	25.8206	144.705
0.4	31.223	157.048	25.2818	133.632	31.6145	169.421	26.0727	145.767
0.6	32.2282	162.329	26.1059	138.147	32.6727	175.225	26.9594	150.786
0.8	34.0798	171.925	27.5919	146.273	34.5129	185.454	28.4573	159.542
1.0	36.6861	185.313	29.6682	157.57	37.0508	199.562	30.5	171.568

Graph 3.2.1: Represents the first mode of frequency parameter μ for an orthotropic trapezoidal plate for different values of taper constant δ_2 and constant aspect ratios $a/b=1.0, (c)/b=0.5$, Non-homogeneity constant $\beta=0.4$, Thermal Gradient $\delta=0.0,0.4$ and Taper Constant $\delta_1=0.0,0.6$.

Graph 3.2.2: Represents the second mode of frequency parameter μ for an orthotropic trapezoidal plate for different values of taper constant δ_2 and constant aspect ratios $a/b=1.0, (c)/b=0.5$, Non-homogeneity constant $\beta=0.4$, Thermal Gradient $\delta=0.0,0.4$ and Taper Constant $\delta_1=0.0,0.6$.

Table3.3. In the following table first and second mode of frequency parameter μ for an orthotropic trapezoidal plate for different values of thermal gradient δ and taper constant $[\delta_1=\delta]_2=0.0, 0.6$ and non-homogeneity constant $\beta=0.0,0.4$ and fixed values of $a/b=1.0, (c)/b=0.5$ are calculated.

δ	$\delta_1 = \delta_2 = 0.0$				$\delta_1 = \delta_2 = 0.6$			
	$\beta = 0.0$		$\beta = 0.4$		$\beta = 0.0$		$\beta = 0.4$	
	First Mode	Second Mode	First Mode	Second Mode	First Mode	Second Mode	First Mode	Second Mode
0.0	35.9037	180.673	31.7407	159.776	37.1871	199.76	32.6727	175.225
0.2	32.6292	167.656	28.8452	148.268	34.0926	186.346	29.9531	163.463
0.4	28.9851	153.54	25.6229	135.789	30.6864	171.888	26.9594	150.786
0.6	24.8074	137.988	21.9287	122.9287	26.849	156.098	23.5869	136.942
0.8	19.756	120.446	17.4621	106.535	22.3573	138.52	19.6393	121.531
1.0	12.8182	99.873	11.3282	88.3508	16.6832	118.362	14.6531	103.859

Graph3.3.1. Represents the first mode of frequency parameter μ for an orthotropic trapezoidal plate for different values of thermal gradient δ and constant aspect ratios $a/b=1.0, (c)/b=0.5$, non-homogeneity constant $\beta=0.0,0.4$ and Taper Constant $\delta_1=\delta_2=0.0,0.6$.

Graph 3.3.2. Represents the second mode values of frequency parameter μ for a orthotropic trapezoidal plate for different values of thermal gradient δ and constant aspect ratios $a/b=1.0, (c)/b=0.5$, non-homogeneity constant $\beta=0.0, 0.4$ and Taper Constant $\delta_1=\delta_2=0.0,0.6$.

III. CONCLUSION

It is concluded that with the increase of taper constant the value of frequency parameter is also increasing. The results are verified with reference [1,2,3] and are close fit to previous results.

It is concluded that with the increase of thermal gradient the value of frequency parameter is decreases. The results are verified with reference [1,2,3] and are close fit to previous results.

These types of mathematical models are very useful in engineering structures. The main aim to develop such type of mathematical model is to attract the mind of mechanical engineers in that direction. By using such type of models we increase the efficiency and minimizing the cost of manufacturing. Also developing new models to grow the technology towards excellence. So it is concluded that by developing such type of models we increase sustainability by using it in engineering fields like Aeronautical engineering, Ocean engineering, Aerospace engineering, Civil engineering, Mechanical engineering, Marine engineering and Automotive industry etc. Also reduce the environment hazards.

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